

treatments was constant. Poison-food technique was used to study growth inhibition of the two pathogens.

The media was plated into petri dishes and dried for 24 hours. Plates were inoculated with *R. solani* and *S. oryzae*

growth disks. PDA plates without any extract were used as control. Colony diameter was measured 3 days after inoculation.

Results (see table) showed the pathogens were inhibited at all oil cake extract

concentrations. *R. solani* growth inhibition was greater in sal cake extract followed by that in kusum, neem, and mohuwa extracts. *S. oryzae* growth was completely inhibited at all neem cake extract concentrations. *k*

Occurrence of brown spot in rice in relation to nutritional soil status

L. P. Kauraw and R. N. Samantaray, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack-753 006, Orissa, India

Brown spot, caused by *Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito and Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Datsur, severely damaged Mahsuri variety during the 1978 dry season in the Operational Research Project Village of Kandarpur in Cuttack, Orissa.

Fields of Mahsuri in five villages — Athanga, Kandarpur, Fakirpara, Sidheswarpur, and Deopur — were tested

for disease severity. A nine-point scale was used to score disease damage. Observations were made at maximum tillering and 1 month before harvest. More than 14 spots per leaf were counted. In Athanga, rice leaves had type C lesions or small spots. In other villages disease intensity was not so severe. Severity varied with soil nutritional status (see table). Percentages of organic carbon, nitrogen, and potash, and cation exchange capacity (CEC) of the soil were very low in Athanga. Seed was sown late and there was an irrigation water shortage.

In the other villages, disease incidence

was low. Percentages of organic carbon and nitrogen in the soil were medium. Potash and CEC levels in the soil were low. Planting was done on time and there was irrigation water.

Disease incidence was lowest in Deopur. Soil pH was acidic, organic carbon medium, and total nitrogen slightly higher than in other fields.

The present study indicates brown spot occurrences are most severe in soils with high pH, low organic carbon percentage, low nitrogen and potash levels, low CEC and under dry conditions which cause low plant nutrient availability. *k*

Occurrence of brown spot on rice variety Mahsuri at different soil fertility levels and sites, Orissa, India.

Site	pH	Organic carbon (%)	Total N (%)	Olsen P (ppm)	CEC (meq/100 g soil)	Exchangeable cations (meq/100 g soil)			Fe (ppm)	Mn (ppm)	Disease intensity ^a	
						K	Ca	Mg			Maximum tillering stage	1 mo before harvest
Athanga	6.3	0.44	0.040	7	7.60	0.051	4.55	1.233	9	20	8.92	9.00
Kandarpur	6.1	0.58	0.040	6	7.10	0.051	4.00	1.183	16	32	3.40	3.72
Fakirpara	6.6	0.56	0.048	9	10.40	0.102	7.45	1.850	12	20	3.68	4.20
Sidheswarpur	5.6	0.50	0.029	10	9.70	0.051	5.20	2.733	13	48	4.76	5.16
Deopur	5.5	0.70	0.063	6	12.00	0.193	4.30	1.523	11	30	1.96	2.68

^a1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scale of 1-9: 1 = less than 1% incidence, 9 = 76-100%.

Echinochloa colona, an alternate host of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot of rice

M. M. Rahman, A. K. M. Shajahan, and S. A. Miah, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

Sheath rot caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Saw) Gem. is a major disease in Bangladesh. It was first observed in 1973.

During the 1980 boro season (spring rice, harvested in April), rice field weed *Echinochloa colona* (L) Link was found growing near an infected hill of variety BR3, a variety moderately susceptible to sheath rot. Infected BR3 tillers and the culm of the weed were close to each other. The leaf sheaths of

1. Typical symptoms of rice (left) and *E. colona* (right) infected with *S. oryzae*.

the weed were infected. Symptoms were similar to rice sheath rot except that lesions were lighter brown and had whitish mycelia and fungus spores (Fig. 1 and 2).

Infected rice hills and weed plants were collected to isolate the causal organism(s). Growth characters and morphology of the fungal colony isolated from the weed were similar to those of the colony isolated from the rice. Fungi from rice and weed were identified as *S. oryzae*. Isolated organisms were cross-inoculated in potted BR3 and *E. colona* plants. In 15-20 days BR3 and *E. colona* produced symptoms similar to those observed in the field.